

Electronic Supplementary Material (ESM)

for the manuscript titled

Multi-phase model for moisture transport in wood supported by X-ray computed tomography data

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Supplementary A: Detailed mathematical model

This ESM provides the complete mathematical framework for the multi-phase moisture-transport model, complementing the abbreviated descriptions presented in the main text. It includes a detailed nomenclature, expanded transport formulations, and references to relevant literature.

A.1 Nomenclature

To ensure consistency, all symbols that appear in the main text are included here, together with those specific to this ESM.

Symbol	Description (Unit)
\mathbf{J}_b	Bound water flux ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)

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\mathbf{J}_v	Water vapor flux ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)
\mathbf{J}_w	Free water flux ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)
c_b	Bound water concentration (kg m^{-3})
c_v	Water vapor concentration (kg m^{-3})
c_w	Free water concentration (kg m^{-3})
\dot{c}_{bv}	Sorption rate: bound water (\leftrightarrow) vapor ($\text{kg m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$)
\dot{c}_{wb}	Sorption rate: free water (\rightarrow) bound water ($\text{kg m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$)
\dot{c}_{wv}	Evaporation/condensation rate: free water (\leftrightarrow) vapor ($\text{kg m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$)
h_b	Enthalpy of bound water (J kg^{-1})
h_v	Enthalpy of water vapor (J kg^{-1})
h_w	Enthalpy of free water (J kg^{-1})
\bar{h}_b	Average enthalpy of bound water (J kg^{-1})
$f_{\text{lum,gas}}$	Lumen gas fraction (-)
f_{lum}	Total lumen fraction (-)
S_w	Free water saturation (-)
\mathbf{f}	Heat flux (W m^{-2})
ρ	Density of wood (kg m^{-3})
\mathbf{D}_b	Bound water diffusion tensor ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)
\mathbf{D}_v	Vapor diffusion tensor ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)
\mathbf{D}_{bT}	Thermal diffusion tensor for bound water ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
R	Universal gas constant ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
T	Temperature (K)
T_0	Ambient or reference temperature (K)
p_{atm}	Atmospheric pressure (Pa)
$p_{v,\text{air}}$	Partial vapor pressure in air (Pa)
P_g	Gaseous pressure (Pa)
P_c	Capillary pressure (Pa)
\mathbf{K}_r	Relative permeability (-)
\mathbf{K}_w	Absolute permeability tensor (m^2)
μ_w	Dynamic viscosity of water (Pa s)
$c_{v,\text{sat}}$	Saturated vapor concentration (kg m^{-3})
$M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	Molar mass of water (kg mol^{-1})
τ	Reduced temperature (-)
ϕ_w	Free water flux ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)

ϕ_v	Vapor flux ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)
ϕ_T	Heat flux (W m^{-2})
k_T	Heat-transfer coefficient ($\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$)
k_{c_w}	Mass-transfer coefficient for free water (m s^{-1})
k_{c_v}	Mass-transfer coefficient for vapor (m s^{-1})
\mathbf{K}	Thermal conductivity tensor ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
\mathbf{K}_0	Reference thermal-conductivity tensor ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
ρ_{cwm}	Cell-wall material density (kg m^{-3})
$\rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	Density of water (kg m^{-3})
ρ_d	Dry wood density (kg m^{-3})
c_{p_a}	Specific heat capacity of air ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
ρ_a	Dry air density (kg m^{-3})
R_{air}	Specific gas constant of air ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
\mathcal{H}	Relative humidity (-)
\mathcal{S}	State parameter in hysteresis model (-)
q_1, q_2	Intermediate parameters in hysteresis scanning curves (-)
d_1, d_2	Shape parameters for hysteresis scanning curves (-)
H_{bv}, H_{wv}, H_{wb}	Reaction functions for water-phase changes (- or s^{-1})
E_b	Activation energy for bound water diffusion (J mol^{-1})
ξ	Vapor-diffusivity reduction factor (-)

A.2 Transport mechanisms

The transport mechanisms described in the main text are governed by constitutive equations as described in Eq. (6), (7), (8) and (9). The equations are elaborated below.

A.2.1 Bound water transport

- The bound water flux is given by (Frandsen, 2007):

$$\mathbf{J}_b = -\mathbf{D}_b \cdot \nabla c_b - \mathbf{D}_{bT} \cdot \nabla T \quad (\text{A.1})$$

- The bound water diffusion tensor \mathbf{D}_b exhibits temperature dependence given by:

$$\mathbf{D}_b = \mathbf{D}_0 \exp\left(\frac{-E_b}{RT}\right) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where $R = 8.314 \text{ J}/(\text{mol}\cdot\text{K})$

- Activation energy (E_b) is given by

$$E_b = \left(38.5 - 29.0 \cdot \frac{c_b}{\rho_d} \right) \cdot 10^3 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where ρ_d is the dry density of the wood obtained using experimental CT data and $R = 8.314 \text{ J}/(\text{mol}\cdot\text{K})$

The steady state diffusion coefficients are given in Table A1:

Table A1: Steady state diffusion coefficients for Eq. (A.2)

D_0^L	D_0^R	D_0^T
$2.5 \times 7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ (m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$	$7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ (m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$	$7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ (m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$

A.2.2 Water vapor transport

- The vapor flux follows:

$$\mathbf{J}_v = -\mathbf{D}_v \cdot \nabla c_v \quad (\text{A.4})$$

- The diffusion tensor for water vapor is given by (Konopka and Kaliske, 2018; Krabbenhoft and Damkilde, 2004)

$$\mathbf{D}_v = \xi \left(2.31 \times 10^{-5} \frac{p_{\text{atm}}}{p_{\text{atm}} + p_{v_{\text{air}}}} \left(\frac{T}{273} \right)^{1.81} \right) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where atmospheric air pressure $p_{\text{atm}} = 101325 \text{ Pa}$ and the reduction factor ξ are calibrated and the calibrated results can be found in Table 2 (manuscript).

- Vapor pressure based on c_v is given by

$$p_{v_{\text{air}}} = c_v \frac{RT}{M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

with $M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 0.018 \text{ kg/mol}$.

A.2.3 Free water transport

- For the description of free water movement, two formulations are used. The first approach uses a concentration-based formulation In this formulation, the equation is expressed in terms of c_w .

$$\mathbf{J}_w = \mathbf{D}(c_w) \cdot \nabla c_w \quad (\text{A.7})$$

The effective diffusivity tensor, $\mathbf{D}(c_w)$ can be defined as:

$$\mathbf{D}(c_w) = \rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \frac{\mathbf{K}_r \cdot \mathbf{K}_w}{\mu_w} \cdot \frac{\partial P_c}{\partial c_w}. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

- The second approach employs a mixed formulation. In the mixed formulation, the equation tracks c_w over time, while the flux is expressed in terms of P_c .

$$\mathbf{J}_w = -\mathbf{K}(P_c) \cdot \nabla P_c \quad (\text{A.9})$$

where:

$$\mathbf{K}(P_c) = \rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \frac{\mathbf{K}_r \cdot \mathbf{K}_w}{\mu_w}. \quad (\text{A.10})$$

- Dynamic viscosity of water, μ_w , is given by

$$\mu_w = 2.414 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot 10^{\frac{247.8}{T-140}} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

- Capillary pressure-saturation, P_c , relationship is given by

$$P_c = 12400 S_w^{-0.61} \quad (\text{A.12})$$

- The relative permeability, K_r , is expressed as ([Perré and Turner, 1999](#))

$$\begin{aligned} \text{For longitudinal (L): } K_r(S_w) &= S_w^8, \\ \text{For radial (R): } K_r(S_w) &= S_w^3, \\ \text{For tangential (T): } K_r(S_w) &= S_w^3. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

- S_w is given by

$$S_w = \frac{c_w}{f_{\text{lum}} \rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} \quad (\text{A.14})$$

- The volume fraction of the lumen filled with gas, f_{lumgas} , is defined as:

$$f_{\text{lum}_{\text{gas}}} = f_{\text{lum}}(1 - S_w), \quad (\text{A.15})$$

where S_w is the saturation degree of free water and f_{lum} is the volume proportion of the cell lumen.

- f_{lum} is given by

$$f_{\text{lum}} = 1 - \left(\rho_d \frac{1 + \frac{c_b}{\rho_d}}{1 + 0.84 c_b} \right) \frac{1}{\rho_{\text{cwm}}} \quad (\text{A.16})$$

where ρ_d is the density of dry wood, ρ_{cwm} is the density of the cell wall material. This equation relates the volume fraction of gas in the lumen to the moisture content and densities of the various components of wood.

A.3 Energy-related equations

The energy transport and phase changes involve several enthalpy terms. The specific enthalpies for each water phase are:

- Enthalpy of free water (h_w) is given by

$$h_w = c_{p_w} (T - 273.15 \text{ K}). \quad (\text{A.17})$$

wherein $c_{p_w} = 4185 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$

- Enthalpy of water vapor (h_v) is given by

$$h_v = 2060.5 + 1.3798T + 0.84808 \cdot 10^{-4}T^2 \quad (\text{A.18})$$

- Enthalpy of bound water (h_b) is given by

$$h_b = h_w - 1146.4 \exp\left(-14.48 \frac{c_b}{\rho_d}\right) \quad (\text{A.19})$$

- Average enthalpy of bound water (\bar{h}_b) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{h}_b &= \frac{1}{c_b} \int_0^{c_b} h_b dc_b \\ &= -1143.1 + 4.185T - \frac{79.172 \rho_d \left(1 - \exp\left(-14.48 \frac{c_b}{\rho_d}\right)\right)}{c_b} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.20})$$

- Heat conduction, \mathbf{f} , follows Fourier's law with a moisture-dependent thermal conductivity:

$$\mathbf{f} = -\mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla T, \quad (\text{A.21})$$

where \mathbf{K} is the thermal conductivity tensor, and ∇T is the temperature gradient.

- \mathbf{K} , is calculated according to (Turner, 1996)

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{K}_0 \left(0.12 + 0.23 \frac{c_w + c_b}{\rho_d} \right) \quad (\text{A.22})$$

An anisotropy ratio of 2, 1 and 1 is used for Eq. (A.22) in L, R and T directions respectively.

A.4 Phase interactions

A.4.1 Interaction between bound water and water vapor

The EMC in wood exhibits hysteresis, depending not only on the current relative humidity but also on its history of variations. The state-based model follows Frandsen et al., providing a framework for determining scanning curves. (Frandsen et al, 2007).

First, the EMCs on the boundary curves are determined using the Hailwood-Horrobin sorption isotherm model (Hailwood and Horrobin, 1946):

$$m_\alpha(\mathcal{H}) = \frac{\mathcal{H}}{f_{\alpha,1} + f_{\alpha,2} \cdot \mathcal{H} + f_{\alpha,3} \cdot \mathcal{H}^2} \quad (\text{A.23})$$

where $\alpha \in \{ads, des\}$ indicates adsorption or desorption. The parameters are experimentally determined using inhouse DVS tests and are presented in Table 1 of the manuscript.

The state parameter \mathcal{S} representing the relative position between boundary curves is then calculated:

$$\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{H}) = \frac{m(\mathcal{H}) - m_{ads}(\mathcal{H})}{m_{des}(\mathcal{H}) - m_{ads}(\mathcal{H})} \quad (\text{A.24})$$

where \mathcal{H} is the relative humidity, and $m_{ads}(\mathcal{H})$ and $m_{des}(\mathcal{H})$ are the moisture contents on the adsorption and desorption boundary curves respectively.

For determining the scanning curves, intermediate parameters q_1 and q_2 are computed:

$$q_1 = -\frac{\ln(\ln(2)) - \ln(\ln(2 - \mathcal{S}))}{\ln(\ln(2)) - \ln(\ln(2 - \mathcal{S})) - d_1} \quad (\text{A.25})$$

$$q_2 = -\frac{\ln(\ln(2)) - \ln(\ln(1 + \mathcal{S}))}{\ln(\ln(2)) - \ln(\ln(1 + \mathcal{S})) - d_1} \quad (\text{A.26})$$

where $d_1 = -1.3$ is a shape parameter.

The reversal points for the scanning curves are then determined:

$$\mathcal{H}_{ads} = \mathcal{H}((d_2\mathcal{H})^{q_1}) \quad (\text{A.27})$$

$$\mathcal{H}_{des} = 1 - (1 - \mathcal{H})(d_2(1 - \mathcal{H}))^{q_2} \quad (\text{A.28})$$

where

- \mathcal{H}_{ads}^0 and \mathcal{H}_{des}^0 are the adsorption and desorption reversal points.
- $d_2 = 0.88$ is the second shape parameter.

For numerical stability in the UEL, bounds are applied to the state parameter:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If } \mathcal{S} \leq 10^{-12} \text{ and } \mathcal{S} \neq 0, \text{ then } \mathcal{S} &= 0, \\ \text{If } \mathcal{S} \geq 1 - 10^{-12} \text{ and } \mathcal{S} \neq 1, \text{ then } \mathcal{S} &= 1. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.29})$$

The actual moisture content can then be determined as

$$m(\mathcal{H}) = (m_{des}(\mathcal{H}) - m_{ads}(\mathcal{H}))\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{H}) + m_{ads}(\mathcal{H}) \quad (\text{A.30})$$

The bound water concentration at equilibrium, $c_{b,eq}$, and the water vapor concentration, c_v , are related to the relative humidity and the saturated water vapor concentration as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{b,eq} &= m(\mathcal{H}) \rho_d \\ c_v &= \mathcal{H} c_{v,sat} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.31})$$

The sorption rate, \dot{c}_{bv} , which describes the rate of change of bound water concentration due to adsorption or desorption, is modelled using a moisture-dependent reaction function, H_{bv} . This function is defined as:

$$\dot{c}_{bv} = H_{bv}(c_{b,eq} - c_b), \quad (\text{A.32})$$

where $c_{b,eq}$ is the equilibrium bound water concentration, and c_b is the current bound water concentration, and H_{bv} is the reaction function. The specific form of H_{bv} is given by:

$$H_{bv} = \begin{cases} \text{if } c_b < c_{b,eq} \text{ (adsorption):} \\ C_{bv,1} \exp\left(-C_{bv,2} \left(\frac{c_b}{c_{b,eq}}\right)^{C_{bv,3}}\right) + C_{bv,4} \\ \text{if } c_b > c_{b,eq} \text{ (desorption):} \\ C_{bv,1} \exp\left(-C_{bv,2} \left(2 - \frac{c_b}{c_{b,eq}}\right)^{C_{bv,3}}\right) + C_{bv,4} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.33})$$

where $C_{bv,1}$, $C_{bv,2}$, $C_{bv,3}$, and $C_{bv,4}$ are empirical constants. The values of these constants are used from our previous work and is provided in Table A2. The parameter $C_{bv,2}$ is a function of \mathcal{H} , and is given by

$$C_{bv,2} = c_{21} \exp(c_{22} \mathcal{H}) + c_{23} \exp(c_{24} \mathcal{H}), \quad (\text{A.34})$$

The values of the constants c_{21} , c_{22} , c_{23} and c_{24} are used from our previous work and is provided in Table A2.

Table A2: Empirical constants used for Eqs. (A.33) and (A.34)

Constants for calculating H_{bv} in Eq. (A.33)	$C_{bv,1}$	3.8×10^{-4} (-)	Ref. (Dvinskikh et al, 2011)
	$C_{bv,3}$	80 (-)	
	$C_{bv,4}$	5.9×10^{-7} (-)	
Constants for calculating $C_{bv,2}$ as per Eq. (A.34) as an input to H_{bv}	c_{21}	3.58 (-)	Ref. (Dvinskikh et al, 2011)
	c_{22}	2.21 (-)	
	c_{23}	1.59×10^{-3} (-)	
	c_{24}	14.98 (-)	

A.4.2 Interaction between free water and bound water

The sorption rate between free water and bound water, \dot{c}_{wb} , follows the same framework as \dot{c}_{bv} , but the interaction only occurs in the direction from free water to bound water. This is because free water can be absorbed into the cell walls and become bound water, but bound water cannot directly convert into free water. If no free water is present, the water in the lumens is considered as water vapor.

A.4.3 Interaction between free water and water vapor

The interaction between free water and water vapor, which includes both evaporation and condensation, is modelled using the rate \dot{c}_{wv} . This rate is calculated using a water vapor

concentration-dependent reaction function, H_{wv} , as shown in Eq. (A.35).

This rate is computed with a water vapor concentration-dependent reaction function H_{wv} :

$$\dot{c}_{wv} = H_{wv}(c_{v_{sat}} - c_v) f_{lum_{gas}}, \quad (\text{A.35})$$

The reaction function, H_{wv} , is defined as:

$$H_{wv} = \begin{cases} \text{if } c_v < c_{v_{sat}} \text{ (evaporation):} \\ C_{wv,1} \exp\left(-C_{wv,2} \left(\frac{c_v}{c_{v_{sat}}}\right)^{C_{wv,3}}\right) + C_{wv,4} \\ \text{if } c_v > c_{v_{sat}} \text{ (condensation):} \\ C_{wv,1} \exp\left(-C_{wv,2} \left(2 - \frac{c_v}{c_{v_{sat}}}\right)^{C_{wv,3}}\right) + C_{wv,4} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.36})$$

where $C_{wv,1}$, $C_{wv,2}$, $C_{wv,3}$, and $C_{wv,4}$ are empirical constants (defined in Table A3) that define the maximum and minimum values of the reaction function. $C_{wv,2}$ specifies the range where $C_{wv,4}$ is applied, and $C_{wv,3}$ controls the transition between $C_{wv,1}$ and $C_{wv,4}$.

Table A3: Empirical constants for Eq. (A.36)

$C_{wv,1}$	$C_{wv,2}$	$C_{wv,3}$	$C_{wv,4}$
1×10^7 (-)	20 (-)	50 (-)	10000 (-)

A.5 Auxiliary relations

- The saturated water vapor concentration, $c_{v_{sat}}$, is given by (Eitelberger, 2011):

$$c_{v_{sat}} = \frac{M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{RT} 2.2064 \cdot 10^7 \exp\left\{\frac{647.14}{T} (-7.85823 \cdot \tau + 1.83991 \cdot \tau^{1.5} - 11.7811 \cdot \tau^3 + 22.6705 \cdot \tau^{3.5} - 15.9393 \cdot \tau^4 + 1.77516 \cdot \tau^{7.5})\right\} \quad (\text{A.37})$$

where $M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the molar mass of water, R is the universal gas constant, T is the temperature, and

$$\tau = 1 - \frac{T}{647.14}. \quad (\text{A.38})$$

This equation provides the maximum amount of water vapor that can exist in the air at a given temperature.

A.6 Initial and boundary conditions

The initial conditions of the model are crucial for setting the stage for the simulation of moisture transport. In this study, the initial free water concentration, $c_{w,ini}$, is not assumed to be zero, as is often done in other models. Instead, it is fitted based on the μ CT results. This is a significant departure from traditional approaches and allows for a more accurate representation of the initial moisture state of the wood, especially when the moisture content is above the FSP.

The initial water vapor concentration, $c_{v,ini}$, is set to the saturated vapor concentration, $c_{v,sat}$, which is estimated based on the initial relative humidity conditions. Since the wood samples are initially submerged in water, the RH is assumed to be very close to 100%, leading to a high initial water vapor concentration.

The initial bound water concentration, $c_{b,ini}$, is chosen to be in equilibrium with the initial water vapor concentration. This is based on the assumption that the wood has reached a state of equilibrium with the surrounding environment before the drying process begins.

The boundary conditions define how moisture interacts with the wood at its surfaces. In this model, no free water at the boundary surface is considered. In this case, the free water flux is zero, and only the water vapor flux needs to be considered. The water vapor flux, ϕ_v , is modeled using a convective boundary condition:

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_v &= k_{c_v} (c_v - c_{v,0}) f_{lum} \\ \phi_w &= 0 \\ \phi_b &= 0\end{aligned}\tag{A.39}$$

where k_{c_v} is a mass transfer coefficient for water vapor, c_v is the water vapor concentration at the surface, and $c_{v,0}$ is the water vapor concentration in the surrounding environment.

$$\begin{aligned}k_{c_v} &= \frac{k_T}{\rho_a c_{p_a}} \\ \rho_a &= \frac{p_{atm} - p_v}{R_{air} T}\end{aligned}\tag{A.40}$$

where ρ_a is dry density of air, R_{air} is the specific gas constant of air ($R_{air} = 287.058 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and c_{p_a} is the specific isobaric heat capacity ($c_{p_a} = 1009 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$).

This boundary condition assumes that the water vapor flux is proportional to the difference in water vapor concentration between the wood surface and the surrounding environment. In this case, the gas-filled volume fraction of the lumen, $f_{lum, gas}$, is equal to the total volume fraction of the lumen, f_{lum} , since there is no free water present.

During drying, when free water is present within the wood, the water vapor concentration

inside the lumen is assumed to be at saturation ($c_{v,sat}$), while the surrounding air has a lower vapor concentration ($c_{v,0}$). Due to this concentration gradient and the boundary condition, free water in the lumen evaporates to maintain the saturated vapor concentration until all the free water is depleted. This evaporation process leads to a significant temperature drop due to the latent heat of vaporization of water.

The heat flux across the boundary, ϕ_T , is not solely due to thermal conduction but also includes contributions from moisture transport. It is given by:

$$\phi_T = k_T (T - T_0) + k_{c_v} (c_v - c_{v,0}) f_{lum} h_v \quad (\text{A.41})$$

where k_T is the heat transfer coefficient, T is the temperature at the wood surface, T_0 is the temperature of the distant air, and h_v is the enthalpy of water vapor.

The system of partial differential equations governing the transport and interaction of bound water (c_b), vapor (c_v), and liquid water (c_w), along with the temperature field (T), can be expressed in their weak forms. The integration over the volume V and surface S ensures the equations are satisfied in an average sense, suitable for finite element discretization. The weak form equations for these fields, considering contributions from diffusion, convection, and sources/sinks, are presented below.

For bound water concentration:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_V \delta c_b \frac{\partial c_b}{\partial t} dV + \int_V \nabla \delta c_b \cdot \mathbf{D}_b \cdot \nabla c_b dV + \int_V \nabla \delta c_b \cdot \mathbf{D}_{bT} \cdot \nabla T dV \\ - \int_V \delta c_b \dot{c}_{bv} dV - \int_V \delta c_b \dot{c}_{wb} dV + \int_S \delta c_b \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{J}_b dS = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.42})$$

For water vapor concentration:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_V \delta c_v \frac{\partial (c_v f_{lum, gas})}{\partial t} dV + \int_V \nabla \delta c_v \cdot \mathbf{D}_v \cdot \nabla c_v f_{lum, gas} dV \\ + \int_V \delta c_v \dot{c}_{bv} dV - \int_V \delta c_v \dot{c}_{wv} dV + \int_S \delta c_v \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{J}_v f_{lum, gas} dS = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.43})$$

For free water concentration:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_V \delta c_w \frac{\partial c_w}{\partial t} dV + \int_V \nabla \delta c_w \cdot \rho_{H_2O} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{K}_r \mathbf{K}_w}{\mu_w} \cdot \nabla (P_g - P_c) dV \\ + \int_V \delta c_w \dot{c}_{wb} dV + \int_V \delta c_w \dot{c}_{wv} dV + \int_S \delta c_w \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{J}_w dS = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.44})$$

For the temperature field:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_V \delta T \frac{\partial(\rho h)}{\partial t} dV + \int_V \nabla \delta T \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla T dV \\
& + \int_V \nabla \delta T \cdot \mathbf{D}_b \cdot \nabla c_b \bar{h}_b dV + \int_V \nabla \delta T \cdot \mathbf{D}_{bT} \cdot \nabla T \bar{h}_b dV \\
& + \int_V \nabla \delta T \cdot \mathbf{D}_v \cdot \nabla c_v h_v f_{\text{lumgas}} dV + \int_V \nabla \delta T \cdot \rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{K}_r \mathbf{K}_w}{\mu_w} \cdot \nabla (P_g - P_c) h_w dV \\
& - \int_V \delta T \dot{c}_{bv} (h_v - h_b) dV - \int_V \delta T \dot{c}_{wb} (h_w - h_b) dV - \int_V \delta T \dot{c}_{wv} (h_w - h_v) dV \\
& + \int_S \delta T \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{J}_b h_b dS + \int_S \delta T \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{J}_v h_v f_{\text{lumgas}} dS \\
& + \int_S \delta T \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{J}_w h_w dS + \int_S \delta T \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{f} dS = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{A.45}$$

In these equations, δc_b , δc_v , δc_w , and δT represent arbitrary test functions, and \mathbf{n} is the outward unit normal vector on the surface S .

For the numerical implementation of these equations, interpolation functions are employed to define the fields c_b , c_v , c_w , and T in terms of their nodal values c_b^M , c_v^N , c_w^O , and T^P . These fields are discretized using the finite element method (FEM), which approximates the continuous fields within each element of the computational domain with polynomial basis functions. The backward Euler method is utilized for time discretization, where the time derivative is approximated using values at the current and previous time steps.

The integrals over the volume V and surface S in the weak form equations are transformed into summations over finite regions (the finite elements) and techniques, such as the Gaussian quadrature, are used for numerical integration. Here, integrals are approximated by weighted sums of function values at specific points, so-called integration points, within each element.

The discretized equations for the fields c_b , c_v , c_w , and T yield the residual equations $F_{c_b}^M$, $F_{c_v}^N$, $F_{c_w}^O$, and F_T^P , respectively, which are set to zero. These equations are coupled and solved simultaneously, resulting in a system of equations at each integration point:

$$\begin{bmatrix}
\frac{\partial F_{c_b}^M}{\partial c_b^Q} & \frac{\partial F_{c_b}^M}{\partial c_v^R} & \frac{\partial F_{c_b}^M}{\partial c_w^S} & \frac{\partial F_{c_b}^M}{\partial T^T} \\
\frac{\partial F_{c_v}^N}{\partial c_b^Q} & \frac{\partial F_{c_v}^N}{\partial c_v^R} & \frac{\partial F_{c_v}^N}{\partial c_w^S} & \frac{\partial F_{c_v}^N}{\partial T^T} \\
\frac{\partial F_{c_w}^O}{\partial c_b^Q} & \frac{\partial F_{c_w}^O}{\partial c_v^R} & \frac{\partial F_{c_w}^O}{\partial c_w^S} & \frac{\partial F_{c_w}^O}{\partial T^T} \\
\frac{\partial F_T^P}{\partial c_b^Q} & \frac{\partial F_T^P}{\partial c_v^R} & \frac{\partial F_T^P}{\partial c_w^S} & \frac{\partial F_T^P}{\partial T^T}
\end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} r^{c_b} \\ r^{c_v} \\ r^{c_w} \\ r^T \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -F^M \\ -F^N \\ -F^O \\ -F^P \end{pmatrix} \tag{A.46}$$

In this system, the coefficient matrix (left-hand side) represents the partial derivatives of the residual functions $F_{c_b}^M$, $F_{c_v}^N$, $F_{c_w}^O$, and F_T^P with respect to the nodal values c_b^Q , c_v^R , c_w^S , and T^T .

The right-hand side contains the negative residuals, which drive the iterative solution process. The vector \mathbf{r} contains the corrections to the nodal values, and the system is solved iteratively using a modified Newton method. To ensure accurate and stable numerical solutions, specific numerical techniques are employed. Upstream weighting (used to stabilize the convective terms in the transport equations) (Diersch and Perrochet, 1999) and mass lumping (diagonalizing mass matrix) are used to address the non-linearity of the equations and ensure stability. These techniques help to improve the convergence of the solution and improves computational efficiency.

The model is implemented using hexahedral elements with linear shape functions via a UEL subroutine in the commercial finite element software Abaqus 2023. The implementation is done using the modified Newton method which is a robust iterative solver of Abaqus that can efficiently handle the non-linear system of equations arising from the model. Each element has 8 nodes, and each node has 4 degrees of freedom (DOFs): c_b , c_v , c_w , and T . These DOFs are represented by the Abaqus node labels NT11, NT12, NT13, and NT14, respectively. The field outputs are extracted for further analysis. The model utilizes a mesh with 4200 nodes. Python scripts are used to extract average node data and path data from the Abaqus output database (ODB) files.

Supplementary B: UEL workflow and implementation in Abaqus

A custom UEL is written in Fortran and integrated into Abaqus to simulate coupled heat and moisture transport in wood. It models the dynamic interactions among bound water, free water, and vapor, including phase transitions and energy exchange. The subroutine's structure comprises three primary stages: initialization, iterative computations at integration points, and system assembly. The UEL operates on an 8-node, three-dimensional continuum brick-element, where the numerical integration of governing equations ensures prediction of coupled processes over time.

- **Initialization:** The subroutine begins with an initialization phase, where physical constants, element configurations, and boundary condition parameters are defined. Fundamental material properties such as oven-dry density, cell wall density, water density, atmospheric pressure, and maximum time increment values (TIME INC MAX) establish the baseline for further calculations. Element-related settings (e.g., DOFs per node, shape-function details, integration points) are also initialized according to Abaqus' framework. Coefficients for surface fluxes (k_T , k_{cv} , k_{cw}) specify the boundary conditions for heat, vapor, and free water transfer at the wood's surfaces. Gauss points and integration

Fig. B1 Flowchart of the UEL workflow used in the numerical model.

weights are defined for numerical quadrature, with the Jacobian determinant ensuring the transformation of integration domains from global to local coordinates.

- **Integration point loop and state variables:** The integration point loop is the core of the subroutine, where local state variables – namely, c_b , c_v , c_w , and T are updated iteratively. Gradients of these variables (eg. dc_b/dx , dc_v/dy) are calculated using shape function derivatives, which drive the heat and moisture fluxes. Phase transitions are governed by reaction functions tied to EMC, typically derived from the Hailwood–Horrobin sorption model. This ensures bound water is consistent with its equilibrium state except when evaporation or condensation processes shift moisture phases, using user defined subroutines.
- **System assembly and stabilization:** After updating state variables, the subroutine assembles the element mass transport matrices. The right-hand side vector (RHS) includes contributions from mass fluxes, heat fluxes, and phase changes, while the mass transport matrix, denoted as stiffness matrix (AMATRIX), incorporates conservation laws and coupling derivatives. Stability checks are performed to identify non-physical values, such as negative concentrations or temperatures, within the solution. PNEWDT, a parameter controlling the time step size, is adjusted dynamically to restore stability if instabilities are detected. For example, if high flux gradients or rapid boundary conditions destabilize the solution, PNEWDT reduces the time step size to maintain convergence.

To address numerical challenges, the UEL incorporates smoothing functions and mass lumping. A smoothing function is used in the UEL to address transitions between free water and vapor at the surface. Instead of abrupt changes, which could lead to numerical instability, the smoothing function introduces a gradual transition using a parameterized exponential function. For instance, during evaporation, the smoothing function governs the shift from free water flux to water vapor flux, ensuring that the boundary condition transitions smoothly. This approach avoids unrealistic overshooting of water vapor concentrations or discontinuities in flux, stabilizing the simulation under high RH gradients. Mass lumping is another stabilization technique implemented within the UEL. This approach simplifies transient calculations by diagonalizing the consistent mass matrix, redistributing mass uniformly across nodes. By preventing oscillatory behaviour, mass lumping enhances numerical stability in scenarios involving steep moisture gradients or rapid transitions between moisture phases.

Implementing the UEL involves significant challenges, particularly in balancing computational efficiency with numerical accuracy. In addition, the UEL’s implementation is inherently

complex and lengthy, requiring significant effort for debugging and maintenance. The coupling of heat and moisture transport equations, along with the detailed treatment of boundary conditions, increases computational demands. Transitioning to open-source solvers like FEniCS offers a potential alternative for simplifying model development and reducing code length. However, the challenge lies in applying such solvers to complex 3D geometries, which Abaqus handles efficiently.

Supplementary C: Sorption model parameters from DVS measurements

The water vapour sorption characteristics of pine HW and SW were investigated using DVS measurements. The measured sorption isotherms are shown in Fig. C1, along with the parabolic isotherm models that were fitted separately for the desorption and adsorption branches (so-called boundary curves).

Fig. C1 EMC as a function of RH for desorption and adsorption processes at 25°C. The fitted curves represent the Hailwood-Horrobin sorption isotherm model applied to the experimental data.

In both the adsorption and desorption branches, the EMC of pine SW was slightly higher than that of HW, which is consistent with the results reported by Ball et al (Ball et al, 2001).

When fitting the models, the limiting values of EMC were required to be the same for both branches.

Combined with the model of Frandsen and co-workers, the boundary curves provide a description of the hysteretic sorption behaviour of wood. The parameters derived from DVS data are used to refine the FE model's prediction of moisture transport within wood. By including the hysteresis effect, the model can more realistically simulate repeated drying and wetting cycles.

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